

EVALUATION OF RADIO STRATEGIES IN PROMOTING SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES IN RURAL COMMUNITIES IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The focus of this study was on the evaluation of radio strategies in promoting sustainable agricultural practices in rural communities in Enugu State. The radio has been an effective media channel for reaching people in rural areas especially in developing countries like Nigeria. However, it is unclear how radio has fared in mobilizing rural farmers to engage in sustainable agricultural practices. Therefore, the objectives of this study was to, identify the types of radio strategies used in promoting sustainable agricultural practice in rural areas in Enugu State, assess the level of awareness. The researcher used the diffusion of innovation and development media theories as the theoretical framework. Descriptive research method was adopted using questionnaire and in-depth interview methods. Population was chosen from four local government areas in Enugu State while Taro Yamane was used in determining the sample size of the study. Findings of the study showed that radio strategies in promoting sustainable agricultural practice was not effective or poorly implemented in rural areas of Enugu State and that radio journalists agreed that they employ strategies such as storytelling, drama, expert interviews, phone-in sessions, community based-messaging and local languages to promote sustainable agricultural practice in rural areas of Enugu State. Furthermore, the level of awareness and adoption of sustainable agricultural practices influenced by radio programmes in rural areas remains low indicating minimal impact. The study recommended among others that journalists should employ strategies that the locals can relate and engage with such as drama, storytelling in order to strengthen community-based strategies and that journalists should strengthen and consistently air sustainable agricultural programmes using effective strategies such as interactive phone in sessions and the use of experts for better engagement of farmers.

Keywords: Evaluation, radio strategies, promoting sustainable agricultural practices, rural communities.

INTRODUCTION

Across Africa, agriculture remains the mainstay of revenue generation for many rural dwellers. Enugu State is one of the states in South East Nigeria that many depend heavily on agriculture for survival. However, modern agricultural discourse and narratives have moved from the conventional subsistence farming witnessed across Enugu State to sustainable agricultural practice which caters for the need of food for the growing population of the state. The need to engage in agricultural practice that does not only take care of the immediate food need of the people but also provide their nutritional needs in the face of food insecurity bedeviling Nigeria necessitated this study.

Sustainable agricultural practice involves crop rotation, organic fertilization, agroforestry, conservation farming and integrated pest management (Restrepo, et al, 2023). The integration of these modern farming practices is crucial in maintaining soil fertility, diminishing soil degradation and encouraging sustainable food security with long-term impact. The whole idea behind sustainable agricultural practice is taking a holistic approach to farming that focuses on long-term environmental, economic and social viability (Chinedu & Okafor, 2019).

Despite the fact that Enugu State has great agricultural potential, numerous communities in the rural areas still grapple with unsustainable farming practices. These include over-dependence on chemical-fertilizers, poor irrigation methods, deforestation as well as poor storage facilities after harvests (Nwachukwu, et al 2022). There are others associated with climate change and variability, land degradation, difficulty accessing modern farm implements, low awareness of alternative techniques and poor extension services. These challenges do not only have negative impact on agricultural productivity but also endanger agricultural practice in the state especially in long-term basis.

In the light of these challenges, radio is one of the indispensable tools for agricultural awareness and education. Radio, being one of the most viable media for rural dwellers, has a wider reach, is portable, and is also relatively affordable (Bello & Salihu, 2022). Radio which is usually local uses the dialect of the people in the community to engage with them. Radio is critical in enhancing the knowledge of rural dwellers about modern farming practices as well as promoting sustainable farming. Radio can reach remote areas unlike television, newspapers and other internet-based means of communication such as social media platforms. Radio stations such as Radio Nigeria, Solid FM, Dream FM, ESBS etc broadcast programmes that discuss agriculture. However, burning questions about the strategic effectiveness of the agricultural programmes in promoting sustainable agricultural practices in Enugu State remain a challenge.

In order to have behavioural change towards agricultural practice in Nigeria, radio messages and programmes must go beyond generic farming advice. According to Adeyeye et al (2021) radio programmes must be intentional and purposeful in designing agricultural programmes. Programmes should be given more air-space, aired in language and dialect that the rural dwellers understand, involve expert discussions and interviews as well as ensure feedback mechanism by the audience (Retkoceri & Kurteshi, 2018). However, it appears that there is limited scientific assessment of how these radio programmes and messages have enhanced the goals of sustainable agricultural practice in Enugu States' rural communities. It is on this backdrop that this study intends to evaluate the radio strategies deployed to promote sustainable agricultural practices in rural areas in Enugu State with a view to understanding their importance, accessibility and impact on the behaviours of farmers in rural areas.

Statement of the Problem

Rural communities in Local Government Areas in Enugu State such as Nsukka, Udi, Awgu, Nkanu East, Ani Nri and Isi Uzo have been under pressure for both environmental and socio-economic factors as it concerns agriculture in the state. Poor and unsustainable farming practices over the years have contributed to soil degradation, reduced agro yields as well as deforestation. Despite government and Nongovernmental agencies efforts to promote agricultural practices that are sustainable, the lackrecognized of proper communication channel has affected its widespread awareness and adoption.

In rural areas across Africa, radio has been as a powerful channel for promoting sustainable agricultural practice because of it potability, affordability and wide reach (Adeyeye, et al, 2021). However, it remains unclear in Enugu State whether radio programmes on agriculture have significant impact on farmer's awareness, attitude and practices. It becomes important to ask whether radio programmes on agriculture focus on sustainable agricultural farming tips? Does the target audience receive the information? Is there a feedback mechanism and to what extent do they encourage change?

Empirical gaps also exist in the area of how radio promote sustainable agricultural practice particularly in Enugu State despite a plethora of studies discussing radio and agriculture (Adeyeye, et al, 2024; Weyori et al, 2018). Furthermore, the effectiveness, structure and limitations of radio strategies have been understudied. This may have been the reason development communication efforts have not done enough in convincing farmers on sustainable agricultural practice therefore, this study seeks to fill these gaps using evidence-based evaluation of the strategic use of radio in promoting sustainable agricultural practice in rural communities in Enugu State.

Objectives of the Study

The core objective of the study is to evaluate radio strategies in promoting sustainable agricultural practices in rural communities in Enugu State. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Identify the types of radio strategies used in promoting sustainable agricultural practice in rural areas in Enugu State.
- ii. Assess the level of awareness and adoption of sustainable agricultural practices influenced by radio programmes in rural areas.
- iii. Identify the challenges hindering the effectiveness of radio-based sustainable agricultural campaigns in Enugu State.

Research Questions

1. What are the types of radio strategies used in promoting sustainable agricultural practice in rural areas in Enugu State?
2. What is the level of awareness and adoption of sustainable agricultural practices influenced by radio programmes in rural areas?
3. What are the challenges hindering the effectiveness of radio-based sustainable agricultural campaigns in Enugu State?

Significance of the Study

The study has both practical and theoretical significance. Practically, content producers and radio broadcasters will find the study helpful in refining their programmes to be more engaging and impactful especially as it regards agricultural practices. Policy makers and government agencies such as Enugu State Ministry of Agriculture will find the study useful as it will provide data-driven insights that can inform future agricultural campaign strategies. Non-governmental organisations as well as farmers and radio listeners will find the study useful in the area of having knowledge of modern farming practices.

Theoretically, the study will demonstrate strong impact on the growing body of knowledge in development communication as well as agricultural extension in the Nigerian context. The study provides a localized understanding of how communication strategies influence sustainable farming practices.

Review of Relevant Literature

Conceptual Review

Concept of Radio in Agricultural Communication

Radio has been rated as a dominant media channel suitable for rural communication especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Because of radio's ability to engage both literate and illiterate

audiences, the radio is perfect for rural areas in Enugu State. It is cheap, accessible by people in remote areas and make contents in local languages. Radio is portable and can be easily carried to farms. Radio does not require constant use of electricity like television and other mainstream electronic media channels.

In communication based on agriculture, radio remains a veritable tool for disseminating information about farming techniques, market prices, pest control tips, weather forecasts as well as government policies such as subsidized tractor hiring, etc. The ability of the radio to engage the people through phone-ins, interviews and jingles, it helps in changing audience behaviour of rural farmers to adopt sustainable farming practices (Farayola, 2020).

Understanding Sustainable Agriculture

In order to fulfil society's immediate nutritional and textile demands without endangering the ability of generations to come to provide their own, sustainable agriculture involves cultivating in sustainable methods. It may be predicated on knowledge about ecological services. There are numerous ways to make agriculture more sustainable (Rai, et al 2023). Developing adaptable farming methods and business procedures is crucial for advancing agribusiness within environmentally friendly food systems. This kind of agricultural practice integrates environmental health, economic profitability, and social equity. Sustainable agricultural practices involve rotation of crops, organic farming, integrated pest management as well as minimal chemical use (Raimi, et al, 2021). However, because of lack of proper education of people living in rural areas especially in Nigeria, the adoption of this agricultural practice is limited. Some people cling to their cultural habits, resist new ideas and have some as a result of limited information refuse to adopt sustainable farming practices (Soni, et al 2022).

Radio Strategies for Agricultural Development

This refers to the various radio strategies which involves the use of programme formats, airtime, language, frequency, and audience engagement methods to reach and influence rural farmers. They include but not limited to the following:

Interactive Programming

This is a situation where the programme content is designed for the audience to be active participants in the programme through phone-ins. When the audience are allowed to call into the programme, they ask questions and make the expert on the studio to explain and go beyond what is scripted. This gives the audience a sense of belonging and being carried along.

Expert Interviews

Expert interviews is an important part of media engagement in encouraging sustainable agricultural practices especially in rural areas. These areas require inviting people that they revere or will listen to who can relate to them in the language they understand.

Localized Content

Content should be created in local languages. Do not see the audience as passive audience. The audience must be actively involved in the programme. To ensure this, the programme must be produced in local language and dialect. Notable people should be used as resource persons experts who the rural dwellers have respect for because credibility is important in this case.

Farm Drama Series or Jingles

Drama series can be captivating and engaging. Using drama and jingles that the people can relate with will go a long way in ensuring that the campaign is successful.

Consistency in Time Slots

It is important to ensure that the programme is packaged and aired at a time the target audience who are majorly farmers will have the time to listen and engage with the programme. Broadcasting this

type of programme during afternoon hours when the target audience are at the farm will probably make no sense.

Encouraging Sustainable Agricultural Practice Through Radio Audience Engagement and Feedback Mechanisms

Radio is a vital channel of information in rural areas, especially where there is limited or poor internet network. It is affordable, accessible, and speaks the local language, making it ideal for sharing useful farming tips. But simply farmers what to do on the radio is not enough. Change only takes place when the farmers are directly involved and their views and opinions matter. Opening up conversations with strong feedback mechanism is essential.

Sustainable farming practice requires relevant ideas that fit the local environment and are readily available and easy to use. When farmers relate to radio messages, they are more likely to adopt them. Their feedback improves programmes, turning broadcasts into dialogues about better farming.

Need to Engage and Involve Farmers in the Process

Engaging and involving farmers simply means to include them in the conversation through calls, texts, contests, or groups. For lasting farming improvements, farmers need to understand, trust, and see how ideas fit their lives. This gives the average farmer a sense of belonging in the process. The issue of sustainable agricultural practice is a development communication issue hence the radio producers and broadcasters must be strategic in ensuring that the farmers are carried along in order to have successful campaign.

For Instance:

Live Programme Call-Ins: In this case, farmers are allowed to speak directly to facilitators and experts who answer questions and clarify issues for the farmers.

Real Live Radio Stories: Success stories can be shared to the listeners about various aspects of sustainable farming which can build trust among farmers.

Using Local Voices: Local farmers can make actual and authentic contributions to the programmes reporting live from their farms.

Using Local Languages and Dialects: This encourages more participation among the rural dwellers and also improve the understanding of the radio message. When the farmers are involved, it ensures sustainability is relevant.

Feedback and its Importance

Feedback is a means of showing broadcasters how their messages are received and perceived. Farmers operate from unique traditions and environments which has impact on how they receive and apply media messages to practice. Without feedback from the farmers, campaigns on sustainable agricultural practice may end up as mere academic exercise.

Means of Getting Farmers' Feedback

1. Use phone texts or WhatsApp messages to allow farmers share their thoughts and lodge questions.
2. Use interact voice which are pre-recorded questions that can be answered by phone buttons.
3. Use quick polling to gauge the effectiveness of the content on farmers.
4. Social media can also be used in gathering the opinion of farmers.

This helps Programme Creators and Broadcasters:

1. Use opinion polls to track adoption and adjust messages accordingly.
2. Clear doubts.
3. Find out emerging issues and address them.

Feedback and involvement make broadcasting a collaboration, boosting community success. It respects existing knowledge and connects ideas to real situations.

Challenges

Various challenges inhibit the successful engagement of farmers in rural areas through radio. The challenges range from poor signals as well as erratic power supply. Radio signal reception in many rural areas in Nigeria especially Enugu State may prove very difficult hence some farmers may not be able to tune into programmes that are targeted at them. In as much as many rural dwellers use battery-aided radio, some people use chargeable radio that needs electricity to function. People in rural areas experience poor power supply hence some people may not be able to charge their radio when programmes about sustainable agricultural practice is broadcast on radio. This can hinder real-time interaction and effective feedback.

Again, there is prevalence of illiteracy among farmers in rural areas. Whenever radio programmes require that they text and not make calls, they may not be able to participate because they can only use voice options. Furthermore, making calls and texting can also be expensive for people living in rural areas.

In addition, some radio stations in Nigeria may have limited means of receiving feedback from the audience. This makes the programme sometimes a top-down communication approach which does not encourage participation.

Radio is a key partner for better farming if farmers are involved and heard. This approach ensures sustainability is practiced on farms, turning farmers into partners in progress.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of this study was anchored on the Diffusion of Innovation Theory by Everett Rogers (1962) and Development Media theory propounded by

Diffusion of Innovation Theory

Diffusion of innovation theory is based on the idea of how new technologies spread through a population. The theory seeks to explain how and why new ideas and practices are adopted, including why they can be spread out over long periods. The rate of dispersion, or spreading, depends in large part on how innovations are disseminated to various segments of society and the subjective perceptions surrounding them (El Malouf & Bahemia, 2025).

Core Ideas Behind Diffusion of Innovation Theory

1. The nature and rate at which novel concepts, methods, or goods proliferate throughout a population are described by the diffusion of innovations theory.
2. Innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and slow learners are the key participants in the idea.
3. This diffusion of innovations idea is frequently used in marketing to better understand and encourage the uptake of new products.
4. To encourage people to embrace new, healthy habits, the diffusion of innovations hypothesis can also be applied in fields like public health (Halton, 2025).

Based on this study, radio serves as a channel through which innovations in sustainable agricultural practices are introduced to farmers in rural areas. The level of adoption among radio users depends on how they perceive the usefulness of the radio information, whether the message resonates with what they have been practicing as well as how the opinion leaders in the community help to sustain radio efforts. In this case, if opinion leaders in the rural areas begin to practice sustainable farming innovations, it is possible that many will begin to adopt and follow their steps.

Development Media Theory

According to Dennis McQuail's (1987) development media theory, the media should help the state and its efforts to promote growth in society. According to the view, the media must be beneficial until a nation is well-established and its social-economic growth is advanced (McQuail, 1994 in Isanbor & Ojebun, 2022). Journalism should support the government in carrying out its policies rather than oppose them. The hypothesis pertains to media in third-world countries, as the name suggests. According to the development media theory, the state has the authority to employ censorship laws to interfere in media operations for the sake of development, particularly when press operations conflict with the nation's objectives for growth (Oluwasola, 2020).

The theory suggests that the media should support initiatives such as sustainable agricultural practice whether it is supported by government or not but in the interest of the nation. It showcases the important role of radio in educating farmers in rural areas, speaking strongly for change in behaviour as well as facilitating access to government extension services in the interest of nation growth.

Empirical Review

Extent of Radio Strategies Used for Agricultural Messaging

In a study by Okoye and Eze (2020) titled Farmers' reliance on radio as an agricultural information source in Anambra State, it was discovered that majority of the farmers in rural areas depend on radio as their primary source of agricultural information. However, the researchers observed that many programmes that focus on agriculture were broadcast at odd times and they were not regularly aired. This affirms the need to assess the depth and consistency of radio strategies used by broadcasting stations in Enugu State in promoting sustainable agricultural practices among rural farmers in the state.

In 2017, Ebeze investigated agricultural broadcast content in five southeastern states. The researcher reported that while over 70% of stations aired agriculture-related programmes, only 30% used engaging formats such as interviews and call-ins. This highlights a potential gap in how radio strategies are designed especially as it regards engagement of rural farmers in the quest to promoting sustainable farming practice.

Assess the level of awareness and adoption of sustainable agricultural practices influenced by radio programmes in rural areas.

Chinedu and Okafor (2019) examined the role of radio in promoting climate-smart farming in Nsukka and discovered that 65% of respondents adopted at least one sustainable practice due to regular radio exposure. However, some farmers admitted they did not fully understand the technical terms used. This underscores the importance of language and audience segmentation.

Similarly, Ifeoma and Omeje (2021) found that radio sensitisation on organic fertiliser increased awareness but failed to translate to high adoption because of lack of follow-up and local demonstrations. Thus, the study calls for evaluation of how radio strategies can be made more effective.

Audience Perception of Radio Agricultural Programmes

A survey by Nwachukwu et al. (2022) among rural farmers in Abakaliki found that while 82% tuned in to agricultural programmes, only 54% trusted the information. Some said programmes sounded scripted or politically motivated. This finding supports your study's objective on understanding the perception and reception of such strategies in Enugu.

Challenges of radio-based sustainable agricultural campaigns

Eze and Okonkwo (2021) discovered that radio was the simplest, cheapest way for Anambra State farmers to get agricultural news. However, programmes were often in English and not in the local language and dialect of listeners, top-down form of communication and not two-way interaction, aired at odd hours while some areas experience weak signals. The researchers encouraged tailoring programmes, using accessible language and local dialect, engaging in two-way communication process as well as improving scheduling.

Bello and Salihu (2020) discovered challenges such as radio stations not inviting experts with in-depth knowledge of topics, poor funding, as well as resistance to new methods of farming by farmers. They also accused producers of lacking development communication skills. They suggested closer collaboration with the audience, improved training, and greater farmer involvement and engagement.

Similarly, Umeh and Ogu (2020) found that in Enugu, many community radio stations lacked content creators with development communication understanding, agricultural knowledge, thereby affecting message quality.

Gaps in Literature

Existing studies in this area of study either focused on message awareness or adoption but did not evaluate or assess the specific strategies used by radio stations in mobilizing the local people for sustainable agricultural practices. Again, most studies have not been done in Enugu State concerning sustainable agricultural development. Furthermore, many researchers have not been able to explore farmer's perception of radio message formats and timing.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The study is anchored on descriptive research design. Since the focus of the study is on evaluating radio strategies used in promoting agricultural practices, the descriptive survey allows for systematic collection and analysis of data from radio stations and farmers with selected rural areas in Enugu State. This design is considered ideal for this study because it allows investigation using a representative population. It describes the prevailing conditions, perceptions, attitudes and strategies employed in the case of sustainable agricultural practices.

Area of the Study

The study was conducted across four (4) Local Governments in Enugu State and they are Udi, Nsukka, Awgu, and Nkanu East. The communities understudy was selected because of their dependence on farming, accessibility to radio signals, as well as diversity in agricultural and cultural practices. Furthermore, Radio Nigeria Enugu, Dream FM and Solid FM were chosen because they broadcast agricultural related programmes within the chose Local Government Areas.

Population of the Study

The researcher studied two main groups as it regards the population of the study and they are rural farmers residing in Nsukka, Udi, Nkanu East and Awgu. On the other hand, radio programme producers and presenters from stations that air agricultural contents also formed part of the study population.

Data from Enugu State Ministry of Agriculture showed that about 150,000 persons are farmers from the Local Government Areas understudy, while the researcher purposively chose 30 radio staff.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The researcher used Taro Yamane formula to determine the population of the study since it is known. A sample of 398 rural farmers were determined at 95% confidence level and 5% error margin.

Census sampling technique was used for radio producers and presenters considering that the number is small hence all the selected participants who were available, about six (6) of them participated in the study.

Multi stage sampling technique was employed in selecting the farmers.

Stage one: Purposive selection of four (4) Local Government Areas comprising of Udi, Nsukka, Awgu, and Nkanu East.

Stage two: Random selection of 2 communities in each Local Government Area.

Stage three: Systematic sampling of farmers within the selected communities. Respondents were included based on availability and willingness to respond.

The instrument of data collection was a structured questionnaire and in-depth interview guide. The questionnaire was administered to the farmers while radio producers and presenters were interviewed. Collection of data was over a period of four weeks using research assistants who are fluent in both English language and local Igbo dialects. The questionnaire was administered by hand while the respondents were guided by the research assistants on how to successfully complete the questionnaire. On the other hand, radio staff were scheduled for recorded interview with their consent sought by the researcher of which they agreed.

Data collected from farmers were analysed using descriptive statistics which include frequency tables, percentages and mean scores. Data from radio staff were subjected to qualitative thematic analysis.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

In line with the research questions of the study, data was analysed based on the returned number of copies of questionnaire. The researcher distributed 398 copies of questionnaire to the respondents. However, 395 were successfully filled and returned for data analysis. Mean scores were used for the analysis.

Analysis of Data

In-depth Interview Guide

Participating Radio Stations:
Radio Nigeria Enugu (FRCN)
Dream FM
Solid FM

What are the types of radio strategies used in promoting sustainable agricultural practice in rural areas in Enugu State by your radio station?

Journalists representing the aforementioned radio stations articulated a range of approaches designed to reach agricultural practitioners:

1. **Language Accessibility:** Radio Nigeria place importance in the utilization of indigenous languages, notably Igbo, to ensure comprehension among farmers. Subject matter experts are also employed to make complex topics clearer in simplified terms during live broadcast segments.
2. **Engaging Content Delivery:** Beyond having a two way communication process, Radio Nigeria engages dramatic and narrative means to effectively convey important agricultural information to members of the public. This method is popular among older people who love culture.
3. **Experiential Learning:** Dream FM incorporates the stories of other farmers who are doing well in their own areas in order to motivate others to engage in sustainable farming practice. Our WhatsApp group dedicated for sustainable development agricultural discussion enhances continuous dialogue and feedback.
4. **Integrated Messaging:** Solid FM incorporates modern agricultural practice guidance into popular music programming to widen audience reach with major target being the younger demography. This approach mix entertainment and agriculture in order to broaden participation.
5. **Demonstration of Impact:** Solid FM use evidence-based approach in trying to propagate the message of sustainable agricultural practice.

What is the level of awareness and adoption of sustainable agricultural practices influenced by radio programmes in rural areas?

6. There is a perceptible impact among journalists though they acknowledged existing challenges:
7. **Significant Awareness:** A general agreement showcases heightened farmer awareness regarding techniques such as manure use, irrigation strategies, and organic farming methods, ascribable to radio broadcasts.
8. **Financial Challenges:** In as much as farmers may be aware of best modern practices in farming, most of them lack the requisite finance to implement what they learnt or heard from radio. Modern farming is capital intensive.
9. **Reluctance to Adapt:** Some farmers in rural areas find it difficult to abandon their old method of farming.
10. **Increasing Adoption:** Dream FM and Solid FM disclose evidence of sustainable practice adoption by farmers in the area of polyculture, implementation of cover crops, and the substitution of compost for lab-created substances.
11. **Language as an Indicator:** Farmer adoption of terminology introduced through radio programs suggests effective message penetration.

What are the challenges hindering the effectiveness of radio-based sustainable agricultural campaigns in Enugu State?

Challenges persist in optimizing programme effectiveness:

12. **Language challenges:** Inconsistency in the use of local dialects, as well as the constant use of terminologies that are complex by presenters, inhibit proper understanding among rural farmers.
13. **Limitation of Resources:** Monetary impediments restrict programme development and sustainability. Lack of consistent sponsorship remains a challenge, leading to programme cancellations especially in private radio stations.
14. **Infrastructural Deficiencies:** Poor radio signal strength in rural remote areas limit audience accessibility.
15. **Poor Time Management:** Programme scheduling often conflicts with peak agricultural labour periods. This reduces potential listenership among active farmers in rural areas.

16. Communication Difficulties: Ensuring an effective interactive communication between farmers and programme used to be problematic. Most times, the phone lines are overloaded and inundated with calls which inhibit immediate feedback as well as question and answer process.

Table 1: Types of radio strategies used in promoting sustainable agricultural practice in rural areas in Enugu State

S/n	What are the types of radio strategies used in promoting sustainable agricultural practice in rural areas in Enugu State?	SA	A	N	D	DS	\bar{x}	Decision
1.	Radio stations use local dialects to inform farmers about sustainable agricultural practice	41	58	62	123	111	2.43	Rejected
2.	Experts are invited on radio to educate farmers about sustainable agricultural practice	38	66	55	117	119	2.42	Rejected
3.	Phone in segments are used by local radio stations to educate the farmers on modern farming methods	49	54	48	153	120	2.42	Rejected
4	Storytelling and drama are used in by radio in communicating sustainable farming messages	52	59	44	120	120	2.48	Rejected
	Mean Score						2.44	Rejected

Decision Rule: If the calculated mean is equal or greater than the criterion mean (2.5), then the decision is accepted but if the calculated mean is lower than the criterion mean (2.5), the decision is rejected. Therefore, the calculated table above is rejected at the total mean score of 2.44.

Table 2: Extent of awareness and adoption of sustainable agricultural practices influenced by radio programmes in rural areas

S/n	What is the level of awareness and adoption of sustainable agricultural practices influenced by radio programmes in rural areas?	SA	A	N	D	SD	\bar{x}	Decision
5.	Radio frequently broadcast programmes about sustainable agricultural practice	61	72	74	95	93	2.81	Rejected
6.	I have learned sustainable farming techniques from radio	78	85	54	90	88	2.97	Rejected
7.	I have applied some of the agricultural practices I learnt from the radio	102	94	61	72	66	3.32	Accepted
8	I am more aware of eco-friendly farming method because of radio awareness	109	88	64	67	67	3.32	Accepted
	Mean Score						2.99	Rejected

Decision Rule: *If the calculated mean is equal or greater than the criterion mean (2.5), then the decision is accepted but if the calculated mean is lower than the criterion mean (2.5), the decision is rejected.* Therefore, the calculated table above is rejected at the total mean score of 2.99.

Table 3: Extent of challenges hindering the effectiveness of radio-based sustainable agricultural campaigns in Enugu State

S/n	What are the challenges hindering the effectiveness of radio-based sustainable agricultural campaigns in Enugu State?	SA	A	N	SD	D	\bar{x}	Decision
.9	Radio broadcasters do not create room for feedback	100	96	70	65	64	3.14	Accepted
10.	There is poor radio signal in my area which limits my exposure to agricultural programmes	95	92	68	65	75	3.08	Accepted
11.	Radio programmes are not broadcast in our local language and dialect	93	90	70	68	74	3.06	Accepted
12.	I do not have time to listen to radio agricultural programmes	98	89	66	72	70	3.05	Accepted
	Mean Score						3.08	Accepted

Decision Rule: *If the calculated mean is equal or greater than the criterion mean (2.5), then the decision is accepted but if the calculated mean is lower than the criterion mean (2.5), the decision is rejected.* Therefore, the calculated table above is accepted at the total mean score of 3.08.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from the in-depth interview guide showed thus:

Types of Strategies: Radio journalists agreed that they employ strategies such as storytelling, drama, expert interviews, phone-in sessions, community based-messaging and local languages to promote sustainable agricultural practice in rural areas of Enugu State.

Awareness and Adoption: Journalists came to a consensus that radio programmes have improved the awareness of farmers and their interest in sustainable farming. However, due to limited resources adoption remains slow.

Challenges: Journalists identified poor signal, language and dialect barriers, poor feedback mechanism and limited airtime as major challenges facing successful radio campaigns for sustainable agricultural practice in rural areas.

Analysis of Research Questionnaire from Farmers

In all, three questions were tested for statistical support. Two were rejected while one was accepted. Question was on the types of radio strategies used in promoting sustainable agricultural practice in rural areas in Enugu State. The total mean score was rejected at 2.44 meaning that radio strategies in promoting sustainable agricultural practice is not effective or poorly implemented. The finding is in agreement with Okoye and Eze (2020) as the researchers observed that many programmes that focus on agriculture in Anambra State were broadcast at odd times and they were not regularly aired. This

affirms the need to assess the depth and consistency of radio strategies used by broadcasting stations in Enugu State in promoting sustainable agricultural practices among rural farmers in the state. This is also in line with Chinedu and Okafor (2019) that examined the role of radio in promoting climate-smart farming in Nsukka. They discovered that 65% of respondents adopted at least one sustainable practice due to regular radio exposure. However, some farmers admitted they did not fully understand the technical terms used. This underscores the importance of language and audience segmentation.

Question two dwelt on the level of awareness and adoption of sustainable agricultural practices influenced by radio programmes in rural areas. The calculated table was rejected at total mean score of 2.99. This implies that the level of awareness and adoption of sustainable agricultural practices influenced by radio programmes in rural areas is poorly implemented or not effective. In line with the above finding, Chinedu and Okafor (2019) examined the role of radio in promoting climate-smart farming in Nsukka and discovered that some farmers admitted that they did not fully understand the technical terms used by media and resource persons. This underscores the importance of language and audience segmentation. Similarly, Ifeoma and Omeje (2021) found that radio sensitisation on organic fertiliser increased awareness but failed to translate to high adoption because of lack of follow-up and local demonstrations. Thus, the study calls for evaluation of how radio strategies can be made more effective.

The third research question was on the challenges hindering the effectiveness of radio-based sustainable agricultural campaigns in Enugu State. Accepted at 3.08, it was discovered that many challenges are militating against radio-based sustainable agricultural campaign especially technical and communication barriers. This finding is supported by Bello and Salihu (2020) that discovered challenges such as radio stations not inviting experts with in-depth knowledge of topics, poor funding, as well as resistance to new methods of farming by farmers. They also accused producers of lacking development communication skills. They suggested closer collaboration with the audience, improved training, and greater farmer involvement and engagement. Similarly, Umeh and Ogu (2020) found that in Enugu, many community radio stations lacked content creators with development communication understanding, agricultural knowledge, thereby affecting message quality.

Summary of Findings

This study examined the use of radio strategies in promoting sustainable agricultural practices in rural communities of Enugu State. The study was anchored on the opinion of farmers using questionnaire and radio journalists using in-depth interview guide. The findings showed thus:

Findings from journalists:

- 1) Radio journalists agreed that they employ strategies such as storytelling, drama, expert interviews, phone-in sessions, community based-messaging and local languages to promote sustainable agricultural practice in rural areas of Enugu State.
- 2) Journalists agreed that radio programmes have improved the awareness of farmers and their interest in sustainable farming. However, due to limited resources adoption remains slow.
- 3) Journalists identified poor signal, language and dialect barriers, poor feedback mechanism and limited airtime as major challenges facing successful radio campaigns for sustainable agricultural practice in rural areas.

Findings from Farmers:

- i. Radio strategies in promoting sustainable agricultural practice is not effective or poorly implemented in rural areas of Enugu State.
- ii. The level of awareness and adoption of sustainable agricultural practices influenced by radio programmes in rural areas remains low indicating minimal impact.

- iii. Radio-based sustainable agricultural campaigns encounter challenges especially in the area of technical and communication issues such as language mismatch, inadequate feedback channels and poor signal.

Conclusion

Radio The radio remains a vital source of farming information for farmers in the villages of Enugu. Radio is incredibly helpful because it can reach a large audience, host programs in the local language, and discuss local issues. We can educate farmers about and encourage them to adopt more sustainable farming practices if we use radio programs effectively. Long-term environmental preservation and farm productivity depend on this. However, there are certain issues, such as poor machinery and a lack of farmers who are paying attention. The radio isn't being as useful as it could be because of these problems. In order to maximise radio's effectiveness, there is need to continue to improve its use, address the underlying issues, and ensure that the programmes are truly helpful and pertinent to the needs and challenges faced by farmers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Journalists should employ strategies that the locals can relate and engage with such as drama, storytelling in order to strengthen community-based strategies.
2. Journalists should enhance accessibility through the use of local languages and dialects. Resource persons must be persons that can speak local languages in order to enhance understanding by the target audience.
3. Feedback mechanisms must be improved while more airtime should be allotted to agricultural campaign programmes through sponsorship.
4. Journalists should strengthen and consistently air sustainable agricultural programmes using effective strategies such as interactive phone in sessions and the use of experts for better engagement of farmers.
5. Government agencies and stakeholders in agriculture should partner with radio stations to sponsor and support the initiative of sustainable agricultural programmes on radio.
6. Media stakeholders should ensure the provision of strong signal in rural areas, allocate more airtime for agricultural content, and ensure a cyclical form of communication as it concerns audience engagement.

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